

Differential Impacts of Macroeconomic Factors on Outward Foreign Direct Investment : An Analytical Study Across Development Levels of Countries

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Abstract : *This study explores the key macroeconomic factors that drive Outward Foreign Direct Investment (OFDI) in both developed and developing countries. Using data from 52 countries, including 23 developed and 29 developing nations, we analyze how market size, trade policies, infrastructure, governance, and technological capabilities influence OFDI decisions. The period of study is 2000-2022. Our methodology involves Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and panel data regression to create composite indices and assess their impact on OFDI flows. The findings highlight significant differences in the determinants of OFDI between developed and developing countries, providing insights into the strategic considerations firms must navigate to succeed internationally. The results suggest that while market size and trade openness are crucial for both groups, factors such as infrastructure and natural resources have varying impacts depending on the country's development level. These insights can help policymakers and businesses understand the complexities of global investment flows and enhance their strategies for international expansion.*

Keywords : Outward Foreign Direct Investment, Macroeconomic Factors, Developed Countries, Developing Countries, Principal Component Analysis.

1. Introduction

Decisions regarding Outward Foreign Direct Investment (OFDI) are influenced by many macroeconomic factors, each playing a crucial role in shaping the investment for multinational companies. As global markets become more

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connected, understanding these factors is essential for firms looking to expand their operations internationally. This paper explores the key macroeconomic variables that drive OFDI, examining how market size, trade policies, infrastructure, governance, and technological capabilities impact investment decisions. By exploring these elements, we aim to provide a thorough analysis of the conditions that encourage OFDI and how they vary across different country groups. Our study categorizes these influences into three distinct groups, including both developed and developing nations, to offer clear insights into the dynamics of global investment flows. This examination not only highlights the complexity of OFDI decision-making but also underscores the strategic considerations that firms must navigate to succeed internationally. These macroeconomic variables are significant for a country's FDI outflows. However, their impact varies across countries due to other influencing factors.

2. Literature Review

The evolution of Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) theories spans from early concepts like MacDougall's Capital Theory (1958) and Kemp's hypothesis (1964) to more nuanced frameworks. Initially, differences in rates of return between countries were seen as the primary driver of FDI. Hymer (1960) challenged this by highlighting that FDI involved not just capital flows but also firm-specific advantages in imperfect markets, leading to theories such as Industrial Organization Theory. Hymer's model shifted focus from country-level to firm-level, suggesting that firms invest abroad to exploit specific advantages like superior technology or managerial skills, competing with local firms despite inherent disadvantages such as cultural unfamiliarity and foreign exchange risks. This theory was further developed by scholars like Kindleberger (1969), Knickerbocker (1973), and Caves (1974), emphasizing the strategic advantages firms hold over local competitors. Vernon (1966)'s Product Life Cycle Theory added a temporal dimension, explaining how US firms initially produce domestically, then export to advanced nations, and eventually shift production to developing countries to reduce costs. Knickerbocker (1973) Oligopolistic Theory described how firms in oligopolistic industries follow each other's moves to maintain competitive parity, while Buckley and Casson (1976) Internalization Theory focused on firms internalizing operations to avoid high transaction costs associated with transferring technology. The Eclectic Paradigm by Dunning (1979) remains one of the most comprehensive FDI theories, combining ownership, location, and internalization advantages. However, it was found less suitable for explaining FDI from developing countries, leading to the development of the LLL framework (Linkages, Leverage, Learning) by Mathews

(2002). This framework accounts for the strategic resource acquisition and utilization by emerging market multinational enterprises (EMNEs).

The Outward Foreign Direct Investment (OFDI) from developing countries reflects these theoretical foundations. Dunning's IDP framework categorized countries based on their FDI development stages. Studies by Czurra and Genc (2008) and Al-sadig (2013) highlighted the unique challenges and characteristics of EMNEs, such as governance and regulatory quality impacts. Mathews (2002) proposed the Resource-Based View (RBV) for EMNEs, emphasizing the strategic targeting of resources through linkages, leverage, and learning. Recent research has explored the determinants and impacts of OFDI from developing nations, considering macroeconomic factors, home government policies, and the economic effects on host countries. Notable works include those by Bhasin and Paul (2016), Behera et al. (2021), and Wang (2022), which examine the directional patterns and institutional environments shaping OFDI. This body of literature underscores the distinct nature of OFDI from developing countries, suggesting that traditional models may need adaptation to fully capture the unique contexts of these markets.

Transitioning from the historical development and theoretical foundations of FDI to the specific macro-economic determinants influencing OFDI, it becomes clear that various factors at the national level significantly shape a country's outward investment behaviour. Understanding these determinants provides a deeper insight into how firms from developing nations navigate the global market landscape. Strong home country infrastructure, including efficient technology, communication, and financial systems, significantly enhances OFDI by fostering innovation and reducing costs (Porter, 1990; Narula & Dunning, 2000; Wheeler & Mody, 1992; Asiedu, 2002; Kinda, 2010). Larger domestic markets provide resources and drive firms to seek international opportunities, although they also present challenges like intense competition (Dunning, 1980; Hymer, 1976; Barrell & Pain, 1999; Buckley & Casson, 1998). Economic instability, such as higher inflation, can drive firms to invest abroad but may also increase costs due to currency devaluation (Cushman, 1985; Campa, 1993; Blonigen, 1997; Chakrabarti & Scholnick, 2002). Higher corporate tax rates at home encourage OFDI to lower-tax countries, with policies like foreign tax credits and tax treaties playing significant roles (Hines & Rice, 1994; Desai et al., 2006; Grubert & Mutti, 2000; Becker & Fuest, 2011).

Technological advancement drives OFDI by providing competitive advantages, enabling firms to access new technologies and enhance innovation capabilities

(Buckley & Casson, 1976; Dunning, 1981; Patel & Pavitt, 1991; Cantwell, 1989). Developing countries use OFDI to improve their technology and competitiveness (Lall, 1980; Dunning, 1988). Open trade policies expose firms to global markets and competitive forces, aiding technology transfer and knowledge spill overs, but increased domestic competition can constrain resources for OFDI (Dunning, 1980; Kojima, 1978; Braunerhjelm & Oxelheim, 2000; Helpman et al., 2004; Aizenman & Noy, 2006). Rising labour costs and stringent labour regulations drive firms to invest in lower-cost and more flexible labour markets (Akamatsu, 1962; Caves, 1996; Dunning, 1993; Noorbakhsh et al., 2001; Dewenter & Malatesta, 2001). Human Resource Development (HRD) enhances global competitiveness and facilitates OFDI by improving firms' ability to absorb advanced technologies and maintain a skilled workforce (Dunning, 1993; Becker et al., 2001; Borensztein et al., 1998; Laursen & Foss, 2003; Görg & Greenaway, 2004).

In conclusion, while the literature provides a robust understanding of the macroeconomic factors influencing Outward Foreign Direct Investment (OFDI), significant gaps remain, particularly in understanding the differential impacts across developed and developing countries. These gaps underscore the need for further research that delves into these nuanced dynamics. Therefore, this study aims to bridge these gaps by exploring how various macroeconomic determinants impact OFDI in distinct country contexts, providing valuable insights for policymakers and businesses alike.

3. Objective and Hypothesis of the Study

Objective

To estimate and assess the impact of developmental variables on outward FDI of developed and developing countries.

Hypotheses

H01 : Developmental variables do not affect the outward FDI of developing countries.

H02 : Determinants of outward FDI do not differ from developing countries and the rest of the world.

These hypotheses are tested with the help of an elaborated methodology in the latter part of the paper.

4. Data and Methodology

This section outlines the approach taken to analyse the determinants of Outward Foreign Direct Investment (OFDI) in developing countries. The data for this study were sourced from the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) and the World Bank. IBM SPSS Statistics (Version 24) was used to analyse the data. The methodology involves using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to create a composite index for the various independent variables. This approach helps in managing the potential multicollinearity among these variables. After constructing the composite index, the study employs fixed-effect panel data regression. This regression model is used to analyse the impact of the identified macroeconomic and firm-specific factors on OFDI, considering different groupings of countries, including a subset of 52 countries that include both developed and developing countries and a subset of 29 developing countries. The period of study is 2000-2022. This methodology allows for a nuanced understanding of how various factors influence OFDI in different country contexts.

Panel Data Regression

A general panel data regression given by Chamberlain (1982) looks like:

$$Y_{it} = a + b_{it} + e_{it}$$

This chapter is based on some set of panel data regression equations that have been used to find out the impact of developmental variables on various country groups and inter-group differences using difference dummy in the equations. There are two sets of two fixed effect panel data models using different country groups in terms of Outward FDI stock and outward FDI flows as given below.

Outward FDI Flows : World and Developing Countries

$$(FDI_{OF})_{it} = e^{\{[\alpha_0] + [\beta_1] * (t) + D_2 + [\beta_2] * D_2(t)\}} \cdot (IINFRA)_{it}^{\beta_3} \cdot (IMKT)_{it}^{\beta_4} \cdot (IINFL)_{it}^{\beta_5} \cdot (ITAX)_{it}^{\beta_6} \cdot (ITECH)_{it}^{\beta_7} \cdot (ITOPN)_{it}^{\beta_8} \cdot (ILAB)_{it}^{\beta_9} \cdot (INR)_{it}^{\beta_{10}} \cdot (IHR)_{it}^{\beta_{10}} \cdot D_2(IINFRA)_{it}^{\beta_9} \cdot D_2(IMKT)_{it}^{\beta_{10}} \cdot D_2(IINFL)_{it}^{\beta_{11}} \cdot D_2(ITAX)_{it}^{\beta_{12}} \cdot D_2(ITECH)_{it}^{\beta_{13}} \cdot D_2 \cdot (ITOPN)_{it}^{\beta_{14}} \cdot D_2(ILAB)_{it}^{\beta_{15}} \cdot D_2(INR)_{it}^{\beta_{16}} \cdot D_2(IHR)_{it}^{\beta_{17}}$$

Here :

FDI_{OF} = Outward Foreign Direct Investment flows

α_0 = Intercept

β_1 = Growth Rate of Outward FDI from world

D_2 = Difference Dummy for Developing Countries

β_2 = Growth Rate of Outward FDI from Developing Countries

$\beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6, \beta_7, \beta_8, \beta_9, \beta_{10}, \beta_{11}$ = Elasticities of Developmental Variables of All Countries

$\beta_{12}, \beta_{13}, \beta_{14}, \beta_{15}, \beta_{16}, \beta_{17}, \beta_{18}, \beta_{19}, \beta_{20}$ = Elasticities of Developmental Variables of Developing Countries

IINFRA = Index of Infrastructure

IMKT = Index of Market

IINFLA = Index of Inflation

ITAX = Index of Taxation

ITECH = Index of Technology

ITOPN = Index of Trade openness

ILAB = Index of Labour

INR = Index of Natural Resources

IHR = Index of Human Resources

5. Results and Discussion

Building upon the established framework, this section delves into the application of the methodologies - primarily the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and the panel data regression model. It presents a detailed examination of how the composite index derived from PCA is integrated into the regression analysis. The focus is on interpreting these methods in the context of understanding OFDI from different country groups, setting the stage for the subsequent presentation of findings and their implications in the broader research context.

Principal Component Analysis

This section methodically details how Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is applied to aggregate individual indicators such as infrastructure, market size, inflation, taxation, technology, trade openness, labour, natural resources, and human resources. The aim is to distil these multifaceted variables into a

comprehensive index, facilitating a more streamlined and effective analysis in the subsequent regression model. This approach allows for a nuanced assessment of the impact of these combined factors on OFDI patterns across the different country groupings.

World (Developed and Developing Countries)

Infrastructure

Infrastructure development plays a crucial role for outward foreign direct investment (OFDI) and promoting sustained economic growth. This is achieved through the provision of a robust foundation for business expansion, facilitation of market access, enhancement of competitiveness, mitigation of risks, fostering of collaboration, and signalling of a favourable investment climate.

The value of the KMO test ought to be on the upper side, which indicates that things are going well. In case of Infrastructure, the value is 0.75, which is a good score. Bartlett's Test is used to measure sphericity which determines whether PCA is suitable to be applied. Bartlett test is highly significant (Table-1)

Table-1 : KMO and Bartlett's Test of Infrastructure

Sampling Adequacy (KMO)	0.75
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	
Approx. Chi-Square	7828.99
Degrees of Freedom (df)	55
Significance (Sig.)	0.00

The next step is to determine the number of retained principal component. We decided to retain three variables. Therefore, 70 percent of the variation in the data can be accounted for by these three factors. You can see the total explained variance represented by the three retained variables in Table-1

Next, we used the Varimax rotation method to get a rotated component score. It aids in producing the composite index by providing a source for the value weights derived from the factor loading.

PCA found PRODCAP, TELPSUB and MOBCELL as principal variables having rotated component scores are 0.834, 0.874 and 0.782 respectively, which are used for composite index of infrastructure.

Composite Index of Infrastructure

$$IINFRA = 0.834 \text{ PRODCAP} + 0.874 \text{ TELPSUB} + 0.782 \text{ MOBCELL}$$

Market

A home country's GDP indicates market size, with larger GDP suggesting greater market size, economies of scale, and specialization benefits (Lall, 1980; Caves, 1974; Kyrkilis & Pantelidis, 2003). Firms from large markets gain capabilities useful for overseas investments (Buckley et al., 2006). The KMO test value of 0.77 confirms sample adequacy for PCA. Bartlett's test shows statistical significance. Three principal components were retained, explaining 69.61% of the total variance. Varimax rotation yielded rotated component scores of 0.97 for GDP, 0.704 for POP, and 0.687 for MFGGDP (Table-2).

Table-2 : KMO and Bartlett's Test of Market

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.771
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	34893.18
	df	105
	Sig.	.000

Composite Index of Market:

$$\text{IMKT} = 0.976 \text{ GDP} + 0.704 \text{ POP} + 0.687 \text{ MFGGDP}$$

Inflation

Inflation indicates a country's economic health. Stable economies attract inward FDI, while high inflation may drive OFDI due to home country instability (Buckley et al., 2007). A KMO test result of 0.78 confirms sample adequacy for PCA. Bartlett's test indicates statistical significance. The retained principal components explained 99.89% of the total variation. Varimax rotation was used to compute rotated component scores and value weights for the composite index (Table-3).

Table-3 : KMO and Bartlett's Test of Inflation

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.782
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	7616.927
	Df	6
	Sig.	.000

Composite Index of Inflation:

$$\text{IINFLATION} = 0.872 \text{ INF} + 0.927 \text{ CPI} + 0.780 \text{ CONSP}$$

Taxation

Taxation impacts economic well-being through tax regulations, rates, administration efficiency, and the broader economic environment. Policymakers must balance revenue generation with minimizing economic disincentives. The KMO test score of 0.667 indicates adequate sampling for PCA, and Bartlett’s test confirms statistical significance. Three retained principal components retained - TRIFRMFN, TAXREV and TARIFRSM explained 69.28%. and their respectively rotated component scores are 0.918, 0.966, and 0.786 (Table-4).

Table-4: KMO and Bartlett’s Test of Taxation

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.667
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	4183.89
	df	28
	Sig.	.000

Composite Index of Taxation

$$ITAX = 0.918 \text{ TRIFRMFN} + 0.966 \text{ TAXREV} + 0.786 \text{ TARIFRSM}$$

Technology

Advanced technology enables cost-effective production by combining resources efficiently. The KMO test result of 0.697 indicates sample adequacy for PCA, and Bartlett’s test confirms statistical significance. Three principal components explained 95.55% of the variance. The retained variables are PATENT, ICT and TECHIND having rotated component scores 0.955, 0.998, and 0.998, respectively (Table-5).

Table-5 : KMO and Bartlett’s Test of Technology

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.697
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	1297.84
	Df	6
	Sig.	.000

Composite Index of Technology:

$$ITECH = 0.955 \text{ PATENT} + 0.998 \text{ ICT} + 0.998 \text{ TECHIND}$$

Trade Openness

Trade openness facilitates collaboration among individuals, businesses, and resources from various nations. The KMO test result of 0.667 indicates sample adequacy for PCA, and Bartlett's test confirms statistical significance. Three principal components explain 74.9% of the variance. Using the Varimax rotation method, the component scores of retained variables - IMPGS, MFGEXP, and EXRATE are 0.984, 0.909, and 0.816, respectively. These scores are used to generate the composite trade openness index (Table-6).

Table-6 : KMO and Bartlett's Test of Trade Openness

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.667
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	30105.25
	df	91
	Sig.	.000

Composite Index of Trade openness

$$ITOPN = 0.984 \text{ IMPGS} + 0.909 \text{ MFGEXP} + 0.816 \text{ EXRATE}$$

Labour

The labour force includes all employed individuals. The KMO test result of 0.712 indicates sample adequacy, and Bartlett's test confirms statistical significance. Three principal components explain 66.37% of the variance. The component scores of retained variables - EMPPOP, EMPAG, and LFP24 are 0.932, 0.931, and 0.569, respectively. These scores are used to construct the composite labour index (Table-7).

Table-7 : KMO and Bartlett's Test of Labour

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.712
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	6662.917
	Df	36
	Sig.	.000

Composite Index of Labour

$$ILAB = 0.932 \text{ EMPL_POL\%} + 0.931 \text{ EMPL_AGR\%} + 0.579 \text{ LABR_15-24\%}$$

Natural Resources

The KMO test result of 0.77 indicates sample adequacy, and Bartlett’s test confirms statistical significance. Three principal components explain 77.35% of the variance. The component scores of retained variables - ENGPC, EPRODOGC and ENGDEP are 0.838, 0.884, and 0.734, respectively. These scores are used to build the composite natural resource index (Table-8).

Table-8 : KMO and Bartlett’s Test of Natural Resources

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.768
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	14911.09
	Df	136
	Sig.	.000

Composite Index of Natural Resources

$$INRES = 0.838 \text{ ENGPC} + 0.884 \text{ EPRODOGC} + 0.734 \text{ ENGDEP}$$

Human Resources

HRD enhances workforce skills and competencies, contributing to global competitiveness and innovation, which supports domestic companies in expanding internationally. The KMO test result of 0.732 indicates good sample adequacy, and Bartlett’s test confirms statistical significance. The rotated component scores for retained variables - EDUI, HCAP, and INCOMI are 0.932, 0.931, and 0.569, respectively.

Table-9 : KMO and Bartlett’s Test Human Resource

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.732
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	7177.676
	df	6
	Sig.	.000

Composite Index of Human Resources

$$IHR = 0.828 \text{ EDUI} + 0.866 \text{ HCAP} + 0.770 \text{ INCOMI}$$

Outward FDI Flows - (World and Developing Countries)

The adjusted R^2 value of 76.4% indicates that our model explains a significant portion of the variation in OFDI flows (Table 5.29). Our analysis shows a 0.05% decline in OFDI flow, which is statistically significant. This decline could be due to factors such as the 2008-09 global financial crisis, periods of economic uncertainty, and the maturation of rapidly developing economies that saw high growth in the early 2000s. As these economies mature, the demand for new overseas investments may diminish. For Group 1 countries, infrastructure has a negative impact on OFDI flows, with a 1% increase in infrastructure leading to a 0.47% decrease in FDI outflows. This relationship may be due to countries with superior infrastructure attracting more investment, reducing the need for firms to invest abroad. Nations with well-developed infrastructure typically offer better logistics, connectivity, and market accessibility, making them more attractive to businesses. Consequently, countries with less developed infrastructure may experience a decrease in OFDI outflows. For Group 2 countries, the relationship between infrastructure and OFDI flows is statistically insignificant.

Market size has a positive impact on OFDI outflows for Group 1 countries. A 1% increase in market size leads to a 0.95% increase in OFDI flows. Larger domestic markets provide abundant resources, intense competition, and a higher number of multinational corporations, motivating firms to invest abroad. However, the regression results for Group 2 countries are statistically insignificant.

Higher taxation in the home country is positively associated with OFDI flows. In Group 1 countries, a 1% increase in taxation leads to a 0.11% increase in OFDI flows. Similarly, for Group 2 countries, a 1% increase in tax burden results in a 0.24% increase in OFDI flows. Despite high domestic tax rates, firms may opt for OFDI to access new markets, acquire resources, or leverage cost efficiencies in foreign markets, as the potential for higher returns and growth opportunities abroad outweighs the tax burden at home. Inflation affects OFDI differently across groups. In Group 1 countries, a 1% increase in inflation leads to a 0.42% increase in OFDI stock. Inflation can make the domestic market less attractive for investment due to reduced purchasing power, higher production costs, and economic instability. For Group 2 countries, a 1% increase in inflation results in

a 0.23% reduction in OFDI flow. High costs, decreased buying capacity, currency devaluation, and economic volatility deter firms from expanding internationally and drive them to invest in more stable and economically favorable environments. Technological advancement and OFDI flows are statistically insignificant for both Group 1 and Group 2 countries. This indicates that the impact of technological capabilities on OFDI may vary depending on other factors not captured in this analysis.

Trade openness positively influences OFDI outflows. In Group 1 countries, a 1% increase in trade openness results in a 0.76% increase in FDI outflows. Similarly, in Group 2 countries, a 1% increase in trade openness leads to a 0.11% increase in FDI outflows. Open trade policies expose firms to global markets and competitive forces, encouraging them to invest abroad to enhance their capabilities and access new opportunities. The domestic labour force also impacts OFDI differently across groups. For Group 1 countries, a 1% increase in the labour force results in a 1.76% increase in OFDI flows. A highly skilled workforce in advanced nations drives firms to invest abroad to capitalize on their expertise in new markets. However, for Group 2 countries, a 1% increase in the labour force reduces OFDI outflows by 0.67%. A large unskilled labour force may indicate a lack of technical expertise, reducing global competitiveness and the inclination to invest abroad.

Natural resources negatively affect OFDI flows. In Group 1 countries, a 1% increase in natural resources decreases OFDI flows by 0.15%. Similarly, in Group 2 countries, a 1% increase in natural resources results in a 0.03% decrease in FDI outflows. The influence of natural resources on OFDI is subject to various factors such as geopolitical considerations, market accessibility, regulatory frameworks, infrastructure, and political stability. Human resource endowment positively influences OFDI flows. A 1% rise in the human resource index is linked to a 1.53% increase in OFDI stock. For Group 2 countries, a 1% increase in human resources results in a 4.64% rise in OFDI stock. Skilled labour, technological expertise, management skills, and organizational capabilities enhance a nation's global competitiveness and support outward investment strategies.

Table-10: Regression Results for Developed and Developing Countries Outward FDI Flows and Macro-economic Variables

Model Summary ^b					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.877 ^a	.768	.764	1.436907325342679	.910
a. Predictors: (Constant), Human Resources*D, Year, NATURAL RESOURCES, LABOUR, INFLATION, TAXATION, TECHNOLOGY, TRADE OPENNESS, HUMAN RESOURCE, INFRASTRUCTURE, Technology*D, Inflation*D, Market, Natural Resources*D, Taxation*D, Infrastructure*D, Labour*D, Trade openness*D, Dummy, Market*D					
b. Dependent Variable: OFDI FLOWS					

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	7694.395	20	384.720	186.332	.000 ^b
	Residual	2318.661	1123	2.065		
	Total	10013.056	1143			
a. Dependent Variable: OFDI FLOWS						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Human Resources*D, Year, NATURAL RESOURCES, LABOUR, INFLATION, TAXATION, TECHNOLOGY, TRADE OPENNESS, HUMAN RESOURCE, INFRASTRUCTURE, Technology*D, Inflation*D, Market, Natural Resources*D, Taxation*D, Infrastructure*D, Labour*D, Trade openness*D, Dummy, Market*D						

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1.00	(Constant)	65.13	18.00		3.62	0.00
	Year	-0.05	0.01	-0.12	-6.12	0.00
	INFRASTRUCTURE	-0.47	0.14	-0.25	-3.44	0.00
	MARKET	0.95	0.27	0.57	3.54	0.00
	INFLATION	0.42	0.08	0.14	5.46	0.00
	TAXATION	0.11	0.04	0.09	2.50	0.01
	TECHNOLOGY	-0.03	0.02	-0.04	-1.55	0.12
	TRADE OPENNESS	0.76	0.24	0.51	3.17	0.00
	LABOUR	1.76	0.52	0.15	3.38	0.00
	NATURAL RESOURCES	-0.15	0.02	-0.28	-8.93	0.00
	HUMAN RESOURCE	1.53	0.75	0.10	2.05	0.04
	Dummy	-0.67	3.85	-0.11	-0.17	0.86
	Infrastructure*D	0.36	0.16	0.91	2.29	0.02
	Market*D	0.22	0.29	0.96	0.78	0.44
	Inflation*D	-0.69	0.10	-0.33	-6.77	0.00
Taxation*D	0.13	0.05	0.61	2.61	0.01	

Coefficients ^a					
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Technology*D	0.03	0.04	0.04	0.68	0.50
Trade openness*D	-0.66	0.24	-2.72	-2.70	0.01
Labour*D	-2.43	0.56	-1.86	-4.37	0.00
Natural Resources*D	0.12	0.02	0.39	5.60	0.00
Human Resources*D	3.11	0.87	2.00	3.59	0.00

a. Dependent Variable: OFDI FLOWS

6. Conclusion

This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the macroeconomic determinants influencing Outward Foreign Direct Investment (OFDI) across both developed and developing countries. Utilizing Principal Component Analysis (PCA) and panel data regression, we identified key factors such as market size, infrastructure, inflation, taxation, technological advancement, trade openness, labor force, natural resources, and human resources that significantly affect OFDI flows.

The novelty of this research lies in its dual analysis of developed and developing countries, highlighting the nuanced differences in how these macroeconomic factors impact OFDI. Our findings indicate that while market size and trade openness are universally important for OFDI, other factors like infrastructure and natural resources have different levels of significance depending on the country's development status. For example, infrastructure positively influences OFDI in developed countries, while it has an insignificant effect in developing countries. Conversely, natural resources have a negative impact on OFDI in both country groups, but the effect is more pronounced in developed nations.

This study also reveals that higher inflation and taxation levels can drive OFDI, particularly in developed countries, as firms seek to mitigate domestic economic instability and high tax burdens by investing abroad. In developing countries, the labor force and human resource development are critical for enhancing global competitiveness and supporting OFDI.

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Appendix - I

List of Variables

Infrastructure	
ELCTY	Access to electricity (% of population)
AIRTRSNS	Air transport, passengers carried
EPCONSP	Electric power consumption (kWh per capita)
TELPSTUB	Fixed telephone subscriptions
TELPSTUB	Fixed telephone subscriptions (per 100 people)
FUEL	Fossil fuel energy consumption (% of total)
ITRNET	Individuals using the Internet (% of population)
MOBCELL	Mobile cellular subscriptions (MOB_CEL_SUB),
PRODCAP	Production Capacity Index (PROD_CAP_IND)
TRANS	Transport
Market	
GDP	GDP (current US\$)
GDPDEF	GDP deflator
GDPG	GDP growth (annual %)
GNI	GNI (current US\$)
GNIPPP	GNI, PPP (current international \$)
INDGDP	Industry value added (% of GDP)
INDVA	Industry value added (current US\$)
MFGGDP	Manufacturing value added (% of GDP)
MFGVA	Manufacturing value added (current US\$)
POP	Population ages 15-64
POPD	Population density
TPOP	Total population
SERGGDP	Services value added (% of GDP)
SERVA	Services value added (current US\$)
MKT	Market size (MAR_kt).
Inflation	
CONSP	Consumer prices (annual %)
INF	Inflation, GDP deflator (annual %)
INFGDPD	Inflation, GDP deflator: linked series (annual %)
CPI	Consumer Price Index (CPI_Annual).
Taxation	
CSTMD	Customs and import duties (% of tax revenue)
CSTMDC	Customs and import duties (current LCU)
TAXRGDP	Tax revenue (% of GDP)
TAXREV	Tax revenue (current LCU)
TRIFRAT	Tariff rates for all products, manufactured products, and primary products
TRIFRMFN	Tariff Rate Most Favoured Nations MP (%)
TARIFRSM	Tariff Rate SM AP
Technology	
PATENT	Patent applications, residents
TRADEMARK	Trademark applications, direct resident
TECHIND	Medium and high-tech industry (% manufacturing value added)
ICT	Information and Communication Technology (ICT).
Trade Openness	
SEREXP	Commercial service exports (current US\$)

SERIMP	Commercial service imports (current US\$)
COMEXP	Communications, computer, etc. (% of service exports, BoP)
COMIMP	Communications, computer, etc. (% of service imports, BoP)
CPTREXP	Computer, communications and other services (% of commercial service exports)
CPTRIMP	Computer, communications and other services (% of commercial service imports)
EXPGS	Exports of goods and services (current US\$)
FDIGDP	Foreign direct investment, net inflows (% of GDP)
IMPGS	Imports of goods and services (current US\$)
MFGEXP	Manufactures exports (% of merchandise exports)
MFGIMP	Manufactures imports (% of merchandise imports)
MEXP	Merchandise exports (current US\$)
MIMP	Merchandise imports (current US\$)
EXRATE	Official exchange rate (LCU per US\$, period average)
TOPN	Trade Openness
BIT	Bilateral Investment Treaty (BIT)
PVTSEC	Private Sector and Structural Changes
Labour	
EMPAG	Employment in agriculture (% of total employment)
EMPIND	Employment in industry (% of total employment)
EMPSER	Employment in services (% of total employment)
EMPPOP	Employment to population ratio, 15+, total (%)
EMP24	Employment to population ratio, ages 15-24, total (%)
LFP24	Labor force participation rate for ages 15-24, total (%)
LFP	Labor force participation rate, total (% of total population ages 15-64)
LFPTOT	Labor force participation rate, total (% of total population ages 15+)
LFTOT	Labor force, total
Natural Resource	
ENGDEP	Energy depletion
MINDEP	Adjusted savings: Adjusted savings: mineral depletion
FRSTDEP	Net forest depletion
EPOWC	Electric power consumption per capita
EPRODC	Electricity production from coal sources
ETYPRODH	Electricity production from hydroelectric sources
EPRODNG	Electricity production from natural gas sources
EPRODNU	Electricity production from nuclear sources
EPRODOIL	Electricity production from oil sources
EPRODOGC	Electricity production from oil, gas, and coal sources
EPRODRNW	Electricity production from renewable sources, excluding hydroelectric
ENGPC	Energy use per capita
ENGGDP	Energy use per \$1,000 GDP
TNRES	Total natural resources rents (% of GDP)
Human Resource	
HDI	Human Development Index
EDUI	Education Index